

DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2021.1
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4954234
UDC: 352.07
JEL: O20

DIAGNOSIS OF THE STATE OF ACTIVITY OF THE UNITED TERRITORIAL COMMUNITIES OF THE ODESSA REGION AND ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR TERRITORIES

ДІАГНОСТИКА СТАНУ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ ОБ'ЄДНАНИХ ТЕРИТОРІАЛЬНИХ ГРОМАД ОДЕСЬКОЇ ОБЛАСТІ ТА АНАЛІЗ РОЗВИТКУ ЇХ ТЕРИТОРІЙ

Oleksandr S. Balan, DEcon, Professor
Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0001-6711-5687
E-mail: shurabalan@gmail.com

Natalia A. Dobrianska, DEcon, Professor
Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0002-0826-8840
Email: semen-198@te.net.ua

Svetlana S. Serkal
Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
ORCID: 0000-0001-5509-1403
Email: serkal.svetocnka@gmail.com

Received 08.01.2021

Балан О.С., Добрянська Н.А., Серкал С.С. Діагностика стану діяльності об'єднаних територіальних громад Одеської області та аналіз розвитку їх територій. Оглядова стаття.

У даній статті проаналізовано сучасний стан розвитку об'єднаних територіальних громад Одеської області. Досліджено та охарактеризовано фактори, що впливають на ефективність розвитку територій сільських об'єднаних територіальних громад. Проаналізовано діяльність об'єднаних територіальних громад, питому вагу населення, доходи та видатки на одного мешканця, видатки на утримання апарату управління та співвідношення видатків на утримання апарату управління із сумою доходів загального фонду. Підрахована кількість та загальна чисельність населення в групах об'єднаних територіальних громад України, сформований рейтинг рівня використання соціально-економічного потенціалу. Визначено проблеми та перспективи розвитку територій об'єднаних територіальних громад як передумови досягнення їх спроможності.

Ключові слова: держава, об'єднана територіальна громада, населення, видатки, місцевий бюджет

Balan O.S., Dobrianska N.A., Serkal S.S. Diagnosis of the state of activity of the united territorial communities of Odessa region and analysis of the development of their territories. Review article.

This article analyzes the current state of development of the united territorial communities of Odessa region. The factors influencing the efficiency of development of the territories of rural united territorial communities are investigated and characterized. The activity of united territorial communities, the share of the population, incomes and expenses per capita, expenses for the maintenance of the management staff and the ratio of expenses for the maintenance of the management staff with the amount of income of the general fund are analyzed. The estimated number and total population in the groups of united territorial communities of Ukraine, formed a rating of the level of use of socio-economic potential. Problems and prospects of development of territories of united territorial communities as preconditions of achievement of their ability are defined.

Keywords: state, single territorial community, population, expenditures, local budget

The importance of considering the chosen topic is based on the fact that in 2014-2020 in Ukraine, a number of very important steps on decentralization were made, by voluntary association of adjacent territorial communities. The process of decentralization was launched, in small communities there is not enough resources to revive the villages and the only way is to enlarge several councils by association.

This makes it possible to use common resources for the development of territories. In our opinion, the united territorial community is a voluntary association of residents of rural, settlement or city council, which borders among themselves. Initiate the associations can both the heads and deputies of local authorities and the inhabitants themselves. The chosen topic is relevant, since the issues of progressiveness of the established communities are timely.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The issue of the effectiveness of the development of territorial united communities and the diagnosis of their activities, was considered by the leading experts of the financial monitoring of the central office of reforms under the Ministry of Regional Development and Scientists: O. Boryslavskaya, O. Drozdovskaya, V. Matvienko

and others. However, it should be noted that most of these studies were aimed at highlighting the positive effects of decentralization, almost without touching the challenges facing newly created.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The article is devoted to the diagnosis of the state of territorial detached communities, analyzes the development of their territories, revenues and expenditures per resident, the level of subsidies of budgets, the volume of reverse subsidies, the share of capital expenditures.

The aim of the article is to conduct research on the state of the united territorial communities in the Odessa region and the analysis of their activities.

The main part

Formation of capable territorial communities, started in 2014, continues today and requires increased attention and in-depth study of indicators of development, financial security, as well as the level of financial and economic potential of communities.

The Purpose is the beginning of 2020. In the regions of Ukraine, 982 combined territorial communities (UTC) were formed. The reform of local self-government and decentralization is intended to ensure the formation of financially capable of administrative-territorial formations of the baseline level. According to the results of research experts, a group of financial monitoring of the central office of reforms under the Ministry of Regional Region, the main criteria for the formation of capable united territorial communities are determined by the community no less than 5-7 thousand people and the level of subsetization no more than 30%. For the analyzed period in the regions of Ukraine, 872 capable united territorial communities were formed. The list and main characteristics of these communities are given in (Table 1) the article.

Table 1. The number of united territorial communities in the regions of Ukraine as of 18.02.2020

Name area	Number of UTC	Laying UTC – Total	Formed in 2015-2018	Formed in 2019	Specific weight of the region of the region to the total number of UTC in Ukraine, %	Specific weight capable of UTC of the region to the total number of Capabilities in Ukraine, %
Vinnitsa	46	42	35	9	4.68	4.82
Volynsky	54	51	50	4	5.50	5.85
Dnipropetrovsk	71	62	60	9	7.23	7.11
Donetsk	13	12	10	3	1.32	1.38
Zhytomyrskaya	56	53	51	3	5.70	6.08
Transcarpathian	17	7	6	10	1.73	0.80
Zaporozhye	56	48	43	12	5.70	5.50
Ivano-Frankivsk	39	33	29	9	3.97	3.78
Kievskaya	24	18	13	8	2.44	2.06
Kirovogradskaya	27	21	20	7	2.75	2.41
Luganskaya	18	17	9	9	1.83	1.95
Lviv	41	40	40	1	4.18	4.59
Nikolaevskaya	42	41	28	13	4.28	4.70
Odessa	37	31	28	9	3.77	3.56
Poltava	53	47	44	8	5.40	5.39
Rivne	45	35	31	13	4.58	4.01
Sumy	38	37	29	8	3.87	4.24
Ternopilskaya	54	49	47	5	5.50	5.62
Kharkiv	23	18	16	7	2.34	2.06
Kherson	33	31	27	5	3.36	3.56
Khmelnitsky	51	47	44	6	5.19	5.39
Cherkasy	57	55	53	3	5.80	6.31
Chernivtsi	37	33	32	4	3.77	3.78
Chernihivska	50	44	37	11	5.09	5.05
In total	982	872	782	176	100.00	100.00

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4].

After analyzing the data in the table, we see that UTC is most formed in Dnipropetrovsk region – 71 of them are capable of 62 united territorial communities, Cherkasy region - 57 of them are capable of 55, Zaporozhye and Zhytomyr – 56 of them are capabilities in Zaporozhye region 48, in Zhytomyr – 53, and the smallest communities in Lugansk – 18 of them are capable of 17, Transcarpathian - 17 of them are capable of 7, Donetsk – 13 of them are capable of 12 united territorial communities.

37 united territorial communities have been formed in the Odessa region, of which are capable – 31 united territorial communities. For 2015-2018, 28 UTC was formed, and in 2019 – 9 UTC, as shown by the data table,

the share of the Odessa region to the total number of UTC in Ukraine is 3.77%. The share of capable of Odessa region to the total capable of UTC in Ukraine reaches 3.56%.

The largest share of UTC Dnipropetrovsk region to the total number of UTC in Ukraine and is 7.23%. The share of Capable UTC Dnipropetrovsk region to the total number of capable sources in Ukraine reaches 7.11%. The smallest Donetsk region is the share of Donetsk region to the total number of UTC in Ukraine and is 1.32%. The share of Capabilities of the Donetsk region to the total number of capable sources in Ukraine reaches 1.38%.

Consider the total population in groups of united territorial communities of Ukraine, which is presented in (Table 2).

Table 2. Total population in groups of united territorial communities of Ukraine as of 01.10.2020

Groups	Grouping criteria	Number of UTC	The total population in the UTC group, thousands	% of the total population
Group 1.	The population of more than 15 thousand people	110	2368.5	22,8
Group 2.	Population from 10 to 15 thousand people	134	1629.7	15.7
Group 3.	Population from 5 to 10 thousand people	277	1944.7	18.7
Group 4.	Population to 5 thousand people	308	1051.3	10.2
Group 5.	UTC-city of regional significance	43	3391.0	32.6
Together		872	10385.2	100.0

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4].

We can draw the conclusions that more than 15 thousand people included in the first distributed group includes 110 united territorial communities. the total population in the group of united territorial communities 2368.5 thousand people. which is 22.8% from the total population of the united territorial communities. Up to 2 groups of population from 10 to 15 thousand people included in 134 united territorial communities. the total population in the group of united territorial communities is 1629.7 thousand people. which is 15.7% of the total population united territorial communities. up to 3 groups of population from 5 to 10 thousand people. included in 277 united territorial communities. the total population in the group of united territorial communities of 1944.7 thousand people. which amounted to 18.7% of the total population united territorial communities. Up to 4 population groups up to 5 thousand people. up to 5 groups included in 308 united territorial communities. the total population in the group of united territorial communities is 1051.3 thousand people. which is 10.2% of the total population united territorial communities. Up to 5 groups of united territorial communities – the city of oblast importance includes 43 united territorial communities. the total population in the group of united territorial communities is 3391.0 thousand people. which is 32% of the total population of the united territorial communities.

The given data testify to significant differentiation in community resources. In view of this, it is necessary to direct the state economic and budget policy to increase the financial potential of the territories that require this, and the maximum possible alignment of interregional financial imbalances in order to ensure citizens a proper level of public services, regardless of their place of residence.

The proportion of the population of united territorial communities, depending on the grouping criteria, is presented on (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Specific grain of the population of united territorial communities, depending on the criteria of grouping, %

Source: compiled by authors on materials [5].

Consequently, according to the results of January-September 20, 2020, the largest group 5, which is 32.6% of the total population, which is located in the united territorial communities of Ukraine and it includes an area of

oblast importance, which follows 1 group, which is a population above 15 thousand people – 22.8%, then 3 groups – 18.7% with a population of 5 to 10 thousand people, then 2 groups of population from 10 to 15 thousand people – 15.7% and the smallest group – 4, which is only 10.2% and has a population of up to 5 thousand people.

Consider the rating of the level of use of the socio-economic potential of the Odessa region, which is presented in (Table 3).

Table 3. Rating on the level of use of socio-economic potential by Odessa region in Ukraine

Name of UTC	The population of more than 15 thousand people	Population from 10 to 15 thousand people	Population from 5 to 10 thousand people	Population to 5 thousand people	Cities of regional significance
Avanhardeysk	8				
Kuyalnikskaya	31				
Oknyansky	47				
Kilia	50				
Thairovskaya		7			
Shabivska		16			
Berezaska		17			
Krasnosilska		37			
Great Mikhailovskaya		39			
Lyubashivska		52			
Shiryaiivska		90			
Mologovskaya		93			
Vilkivska		106			
Vizirskaya			4		
Cousin			16		
Dalnitskaya			48		
Mayakivska			84		
Starocozak			96		
Greatboyalytska			119		
Termikskaya			129		
Velykloskovskaya			132		
Marazliivska			144		
Yakovskaya			195		
Femanda			243		
Novokalchevskaya				33	
Konoplyechnya				90	
Tuzlovskaya				155	
Liamansky				181	
Flourishing				207	
Bilyayevskaya					24
Baltskaya					33
Total UTC in a group in Ukraine	110	134	277	308	43

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4].

Among the united territory communities of the first group, which summarize more than 15 thousand people, the first place in the Odessa region and the eighth of 110 such in Ukraine occupied an Avanhardeysk united territory community. This community is fifth in terms of reverse deductions and donor among large united territory communities in Ukraine. Kuyalnikskaya Rural United Territorial Community took overall 31 place from 110. 47th place in the all-Ukrainian ranking occupied Oknyanka settlement council United territorial community. Kilyaska – among large communities ranked 50th.

Among the communities of the second group (with a population of 10-15 thousand people), Tairovskaya UTC 110 such in Ukraine occupied an avant-garden united territory community occupied 7th place in Ukraine and the first in the Odessa region. Shabivska and Bereziv communities were occupied by 16 and 17 places in accordance with 134 communities. Vilkovskaya eighth of 110 such in Ukraine occupied an avant-garden united territory community there are 106th in this group.

In the UTC group with a population of 5-10 thousand people, the highest among community rating (4th in Ukraine) showed a Vizirskaya. New UTC, who only joined in the rankings of communities of the Odessa region, were evaluated by the rating of communities - Great Buljalitskaya and Velikovskaya – occupied 119 and 132 places from 277 UTC Group.

Among the five UTC with a population of up to 5 thousand people (in general, such communities in Ukraine are largest – 308) the highest rating (33th place) showed an insalable Novokalchevsky united territorial

community. The flourishing UTC took 207th place from 308. The community of the least numerical (43 UTC) of the fifth group in the Odessa region are represented by the Bilyayevskaya city united territorial community (24th place) and the Baltic City United Territorial Community (33rd place).

With a number of indicators, the level of financial security of the united communities is evaluated to perform the tasks and powers they are endowed. Consequently, these criteria belongs to the income of the general fund for the 1st resident (the ratio of revenues revenues of the General Fund without transfers to the number of inhabitants of the corresponding UTC), which is presented on (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Income of the General Fund for one resident of Odessa region in the first half of 2020, UAH.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4; 6].

Considering the statistics of the General Fund's revenues to the 1st resident in the united territorial communities of Odessa. in the first half of 2020. it can be found that the Vizirskaya united territorial community has the largest income (UAH 14514.9). and the smallest income (109.4 UAH) in the Liman United Territorial Community and. Among others. an avant – hard united territorial community – 4400.3 UAH.; Kuyalnitskaya united territorial community – 2636.8 UAH.; Oknyansky united territorial community – 1967.8 UAH; Kilia United Territorial Community – 1499.4 UAH.; Tairov united territorial community – 5507.2 UAH; Shabivska United Territorial Community – 2483.2 UAH; Berezivsky united territorial community – 2004.2 UAH; Krasnosil United Territorial Community – 3612.9 UAH; Velikielivska united territorial community – 1630.3 UAH.; Lyubashiv united territorial community – 1724.6 UAH; Shiryayevsky united territorial community – 1702.7 UAH; Mological united territorial community – 731.5 UAH.; Vilkiv United Territorial Community – 1171.9 UAH; Cosilic united territorial community – 4014.1 UAH; Dulnitckaya United Territorial Community – 1829.8 UAH; Starokozak United Territorial Community – 1456.3 UAH.; Great Buljalitska United Territorial Community – 1457.2 UAH.; Velykloskovskaya united territorial community – UAH 1789; Mazliyivsk United Territorial Community – 1081.2 UAH; Yakovskaya united territorial community – UAH 877.8; Feminent united territorial community – 1128.3 UAH.; Novokalchevsky united territorial community – 1915.6 UAH.; Konoplyechnya United Territorial Community – 1541 UAH; Tuzlivsky united territorial community – 1453.4 UAH; The flourishing united territorial community – 1357.9 UAH.; Bilyaiv United Territorial Community – 2408.4 UAH; Baltic Unified Territorial Community – 2117.6 UAH.

According to the criterion "Income of the General Fund for the 1st resident (without transfers)" in the communities of the Odessa region. the average figure is 2368 UAH.

The expenditures of the General Fund for one resident of the Odessa region (the ratio of the total expenditures of the general fund to the number of inhabitants of the corresponding UTC) are presented on (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Expenditures of the general fund for one resident of the Odessa region for January-September 2020, UAH.

Source: compiled by autors on materials [1-4; 6].

We see that the largest amount of general fund expenditures per resident in such an UTC: Vizirskaya – 14350.7 UAH., Konoplyechnya – 6264.2 UAH., Novokalchevskaya – 6181.5 UAH.. The smallest amount of general fund expenditures per resident in such UTC: Great Buljalitskaya – 2072.5 UAH., Lyubashivskaya – 357.9 UAH., Mologou – 357.7 UAH., Yakovskaya – 391.2 UAH.

According to the criterion "Governmental Fund expenditures for the 1st resident" in the communities of the Odessa region, the average figure is 5159.47 UAH.

On (Fig. 4) expenditures for maintenance of management apparatus per resident Odessa region for January-September 2020 are presented.

Figure 4. Expenditures for maintenance of management apparatus per resident of Odessa region for January-September 2020, UAH.

Source: compiled by autors on materials [1-4; 7].

After analyzing the drawing, we see that the greatest amount of expenditures on the maintenance of the management apparatus per resident in such a holy: Vizirskaya – 1608.3 UAH., Krasnosilskaya – 1602.7 UAH., Tairovskaya – 1444.8 UAH., Velykloskivska – 1145.1 UAH.

The smallest amount of expenditures on the maintenance of the management apparatus per resident in such UTC: Mologovskaya – 295.1 UAH., Great Mikhailovskaya – 486.4 UAH., Berezivska – 501.3 UAH., Lyubashivsky – 545.8 UAH., Kilia – 578.1 UAH.

According to the criterion "Expenditures on the maintenance of the management apparatus per resident" in the communities of the Odessa region, the average figure is 835,38 UAH., And in the Mayakovskaya UTC – 848.8 UAH., that is, a slightly higher than the average indicator in the region.

Consider the ratio of expenditures for the maintenance of the management apparatus with the amount of general fund revenues (the ratio of expenditures on the maintenance of the management of local self-government bodies with the sum of the General Fund's revenues without taking into account transfers from the state budget, as a percentage), which is presented on (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Ratio of expenditures for maintenance of management apparatus with the amount of general fund revenues (without transfers) for the first half of 2020 in the Odessa region,%

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4; 7].

Looking in the figure, we conclude that the largest ratio of expenditures for maintenance of management apparatus with the sum of the general fund revenues for the first half of 2020 by the united territorial communities of Odessa region in the Flourished United Territorial Community (46.9%), and the smallest in The Visner United Territorial Community (6.6%).

Regarding other united territorial communities: Kuyalnitsky united territorial communities – 21.9%; Oknyansky combined territorial communities – 24%; Kilia united territorial communities – 24%; Tairovsky United Territorial Communities – 17.7%; Berezivska united territorial communities – 16.3%; Krasnosil United

Territorial Communities – 28.5%; Great Mikhailovskaya united territorial communities – 19.6%; Lyubashiv united territorial communities – 21.2%; Shiryayevsky united territorial communities – 43.3%; Mological united territorial communities – 24.5%; Vilkovskaya united territorial communities – 32.4%; Dulnitskaya united territorial communities – 25.4%; Mayakovskaya united territorial communities – 29.6%; Starozak United Territorial Communities – 30.3%; Great Bulls are united by the territorial communities – 23.6%; Velikoplocksky united territorial communities – 37.3%; The Marazliivsky united territorial communities – 37.8%; Novokalchevsk United Territorial Communities – 33.3%; Konoplyechnya United Territorial Communities – 31.5%; Tuzlivsky combined territorial communities – 38.9%; Bilyavian united territorial communities – 23.8%; Baltic united territorial communities – 18.8%.

The average ratio of expenditures for maintenance of the management device with the total income of the general community of the Odessa region is 28%, and in the Mayakov, the united territorial communities are slightly higher than the average and is 29.6%.

On (Fig. 6) is represented by the share of salaries with scheduling in the expenditures of the General Fund of the budget United Territorial Communities (interest proportion conducted from the general fund of the budget for wages for payments to the scope of the total budget expenditures without taking into account the transfers listed from the budget united territorial communities to other budgets).

Figure 6. Specific weight of the amount of wages, taking into account in cases of the general fund of the budget in the first half of 2020 in the Odessa region, %

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4; 8].

After analyzing the drawing, we see that the largest share of wages are based on the expenditures of the general fund of the budget in the first half of 2020 in the united territorial community of the Odessa region in the

Liamansky united territorial community (93%), and the smallest in the Vizirskaya Objective. United territorial community (46%). In respect of others: an Kuyalnitky united territorial community – 78%; Oknyansky united territorial community – 81%; Kilia united territorial community – 75%; Tairovsky united territorial community – 47%; Berezhivsky united territorial community – 86%; Krasnosil United Territorial Community – 78%; Great Mikhailovskaya united territorial community – 89%; Lyubashiv united territorial community – 83%; Shiryayev United Territorial Community – 82%; The Mologological Combined Territorial Community – 85%; Vilkovsky united territorial community – 87%; Dulnitskaya United Territorial Community – 71%; The Majakov united territorial community is 79%; Starokozak United Territorial Community – 77%; The Great Buljalitska United Territorial Community – 82%; Velikoplochsky United Territorial Community – 84%; The Marazliivsky united territorial community is 78%; Yakovskaya united territorial community – 86%; Novokalchevsky united territorial community – 75%; Konoplyechnya UTC – 89%; Tuzlovsky united territorial community – 82%; Bilyavian united territorial community – 76%; The Baltic Unified Territorial Community – 73%.

On average, 78% of the total budget expenditures of the Budget, the United Territorial Community of Odessa Oblast are spending salaries, and in the Majak Unified Territorial Community This indicator is a slightly higher and 79%.

On (Fig. 7) the level of budget subsidies (the ratio of the volume of baseline or reverse subsidies to the total revenue of the general fund of the UTC budget, taking into account basic or reverse subsidies, excluding subventions from the state budget) is presented.

Figure 7. Level of budget subsidies (share of basic (+) / reverse (-) subsidies in revenues) of the Odessa region for January-September 2020, %

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4; 9].

After analyzing Figure 7, we can conclude that the level of subsidization of budgets of united territorial communities of the Odessa region in January-September 2020, the largest level of the share of basic granting in revenues was 44%, and the largest level of proportion of reverse subsidies in the monological community Revenues were in the Visner Community – 23.4%.

On average, 12.82% of the level of netting of the united territorial communities of the Odessa region, and in the Mayakov united territorial communities, this figure is slightly higher than the average and is 20.2%. Consider the amount of reverse subsidies, which will be calculated to the State Budget of the Odessa region in 2021, ths. UAH per (Fig. 8).

Let's conclude that the communities of Odessa are transferred to the state budget 588164.4 thousand UAH. reverse subsidies and will receive 884642.3 thousand UAH basic. The reversal will count nine communities: the largest – Odesa city (372425.8 thousand UAH), the smallest – Tairovsky settlement (2254.6 thousand UAH). Other communities: 7866.20 thousand UAH – an avant-garde community; 66319 thousand UAH of the victory community; 4144.60 thousand UAH Danish community; 4629.90 thousand UAH, Nerbay community; 48711.20 thousand UAH of the Black Sea community; 67040.30 thousand UAH. Yuzhnensky community.

On (Fig. 9) a share of capital expenditures in the total expenditures of the general and special fund of the relevant budget of the united territorial communities are presented.

Figure 8. The volume of reverse dotation, which will be counted to the State Budget of the Odessa region in 2021, ths. UAH

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4].

Figure 9. Specific weight of capital expenditures in the total expenditures of the Odessa region for January-September 2020, %.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [1-4].

After analyzing the drawing, we see that the smallest share of capital expenditures in the total amount of expenditures is 0.8% in the Tuzilian community, and the largest share of capital expenditures in the total expenditure of expenditures is 50.07% in the Tairovsky community.

On average, 16.42% is the share of capital expenditures in the total expenditures of the united territorial communities of the Odessa region, and in the Majakov united territorial communities, this figure is 16.5%.

The volumes of capital expenditures reflect the capacity of the united territorial communities to provide socio-economic development, opportunities for the implementation of infrastructural development projects, the creation of material assets or obtaining a social effect.

Conclusions

The given data testify to significant differentiation in community resources. In view of this, it is necessary to direct the state economic and budget policy to increase the financial potential of the territories that require this,

and the maximum possible alignment of interregional financial imbalances in order to ensure citizens a proper level of public services, regardless of their place of residence.

For the analyzed period in the regions of Ukraine, 982 combined territorial communities were formed. In the Odessa region, 37 united territorial communities were captured, of which are capable – 31 united territorial communities. For 2015-2018, 28 united territorial communities were formed, and in 2019 – 9 united territorial communities.

The share of united territorial communities of the Odessa region to the total number of united territorial communities in Ukraine is 3.77%. The share of capable united territorial communities of the Odessa region to the total capable of UTC in Ukraine reaches 3.56%. The largest share of the united territorial communities of the Dnipropetrovsk region to the total number of united territorial communities in Ukraine and is 7.23%. The share of capable united territorial communities of the Dnipropetrovsk region to the total number of capable sources in Ukraine reaches 7.11%.

On average, 28% is the ratio of expenditures for maintenance of management apparatus with the amount of revenues of the general fund of united territorial communities of the Odessa region. 78% of the total budget expenditures of the United Territorial Communities of the Odessa region on average spend on salaries. 16.42% – share of capital expenditures in the total expenditures of the united territorial communities of the Odessa region. On average, 12.82% of the level of subsidy budgets of the united territorial communities of the Odessa region.

Abstract

The article analyzes the current state of development of the united territorial communities of Odessa region. The factors influencing the efficiency of development of the territories of rural united territorial communities are investigated and characterized. The estimated number and total population in the groups of united territorial communities of Ukraine, formed a rating of the level of use of socio-economic potential. Problems and prospects of development of territories of united territorial communities as preconditions of achievement of their ability are defined. The issues of efficiency of development of territorial united communities and the state of their activity, incomes and expenses per capita, level of budget subsidies, volume of return subsidies, share of capital expenses, share of population of united territorial communities depending on grouping are considered.

It turns out that during the analyzed period, 982 united territorial communities were formed in the regions of Ukraine. In Odessa region, 37 united territorial communities have been formed, 31 of them are united territorial communities. In 2015-2018, 28 united territorial communities were formed, and in 2019 – 9 united territorial communities. It was found that the more active the community, the more projects will be implemented at public expense of their own projects. Accordingly, the united territorial community will earn more and spend more on the development of territories. This will be an incentive to attract additional investment. Communities of Odessa region will transfer 588164.4 UAH thousand to the state budget. return grant and will receive 884642.3 UAH thousand basic. Taking into account the statistics of income of the general fund per 1 inhabitant in the united territorial communities of Odessa region, it was found that the Vyzyr united territorial community has the highest income of 14514.9 UAH. And the lowest – 109.4 UAH. in the Lyman united territorial community.

As a result of the merger, local governments are given much greater opportunities for the development of powers and funds than individual villages or towns. After the unification of the territorial communities, the villages received not only the elected governing bodies competent to solve all local issues, but also funds from the state budget for development, which go to the united territorial state directly from the state budget and not indirectly unity.

Список літератури:

1. Звіт про здійснення Одеською обласною державною адміністрацією покладених на неї повноважень та стан розвитку території у 2018 році. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://oda.odessa.gov.ua/statics/pages/files/5c541a5409eb5.pdf>.
2. На допомогу громадам у формуванні бюджетів – «шпаргалка» від центрального офісу реформ. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <http://knt.sm.gov.ua/index.php/en/press/8-novini/7495-na-dopomogu-gromadam-u-formuvanni-byudzhativ-shpargalka-vid-tsentralnogo-ofisu-reform>.
3. Портал «Децентралізація». [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://decentralization.gov.ua/gromada>.
4. Децентралізація: коротко про головне. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://cost.ua/698-detsentralizatsiya-korotko-pro-holovne/>.
5. Добрянська Н.А., Буковський Д.А. Реформа децентралізації як засіб формування ефективного самоврядування в Україні // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2020. – № 1 (47). – с. 57-67. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejoru/2020/No1/57.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2020.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3967330.
6. Dobrianska N.A. The current state of investments attraction into the regional economy / N. A. Dobrianska, L. A. Torishnya // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2019. – № 1 (7). – С. 5-12. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejoru/2019/No1/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3405936.

7. Kulinska A.V. Key aspects of the state influence mechanism on investments attraction by local authorities / A. V. Kulinska, I. R. Kravtsova, O. S. Balan // *Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету*. – 2020. – № 1 (11). – С. 21-28. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2020/No1/21.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.01.2020.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3975501.
8. Добрянська Н.А. Управління інвестиційним процесом Одеської області / Н. А. Добрянська, А. А. Капелюшна // *Економіка: реалії часу*. Науковий журнал. – 2019. – № 4 (44). – С. 32-39. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2019/No4/32.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3757391.
9. Lebedeva V., Dobrianska N., Gromova L. Public-private partnership as the leadership composition of the development of industrial production. 2nd International Conference on Social, economic, and academic leadership (ICSEAL 2018). *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Atlantis Press. – 2018. – vol. 217. – pp. 78-86. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/icseal-18/25904296>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2991/icseal-18.2018.12>.

References:

1. Report on the exercise by the Odessa Regional State Administration of its powers and the state of development of the territory in 2018. Retrieved from <https://oda.odessa.gov.ua/statics/pages/files/5c541a5409eb5.pdf>.
2. To help communities in forming budgets – a "cheat sheet" from the central office of reforms. Retrieved from <http://knt.sm.gov.ua/index.php/en/press/8-novini/7495-na-dopomogu-gromadam-u-formuvanni-byudzhetiv-shpargalka-vid-tsentralnogo-ofisu-reform>.
3. Portal "Decentralization". Retrieved from <https://decentralization.gov.ua/gromada>.
4. Decentralization: briefly about the main thing. Retrieved from <https://cost.ua/698-detsentralizatsiya-korotko-pro-holovne/>.
5. Dobrianska N.A., Bukovsky D.A. (2020). Decentralization reform as a means of forming effective local self-government in Ukraine. *Economics: time realities. Scientific journal*, 1 (47), 20-26. Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2020/No1/20.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.01.2020.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3967330.
6. Dobrianska N.A., Torishnya L.A. (2019). The current state of investments attraction into the regional economy. *Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university*, № 1 (7), 5-12. Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2019/No1/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3405936.
7. Kulinska A.V., Kravtsova I.R., Balan O.S. (2020). Key aspects of the state influence mechanism on investments attraction by local authorities. *Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university*, 1 (11), 21-28. Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2020/No1/21.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.01.2020.3. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3975501.
8. Dobrianska N.A., Kapeliushna A.A. (2019). Management of the investment process of the Odessa region. *Economics: time realities. Scientific journal*, 4 (44), 32-39. Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2019/No4/32.pdf>. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3757391.
9. Lebedeva, V., Dobrianska, N. & Gromova, L. (2018). Public-private partnership as the leadership composition of the development of industrial production. 2nd International Conference on Social, economic, and academic leadership. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Atlantis Press, 217, 78-86. Retrieved from: <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/icseal-18/25904296>. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2991/icseal-18.2018.12> [in English].

Посилання на статтю:

Balan O.S. Diagnosis of the state of activity of the united territorial communities of Odessa region and analysis of the development of their territories / O. S. Balan, N. A. Dobrianska, S. S. Serkal // Економічний журнал Одеського політехнічного університету. – 2021. – № 2 (16). – С. 5-16. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2021/No2/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2021.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4954234.

Reference a JournalArticle:

Balan O.S. Diagnosis of the state of activity of the united territorial communities of Odessa region and analysis of the development of their territories / O. S. Balan, N. A. Dobrianska, S. S. Serkal // Economic journal Odessa polytechnic university. – 2021. – № 2 (16). – P. 5-16. – Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/ejopu/2021/No2/5.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/EJ.02.2021.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4954234.

